

Resonances, Lagrangians and Quantum Propagator/Partition Function

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In classical mechanics, it is possible to have different Lagrangians yield identical equations of motion. For example, a velocity dependent potential $x \, dx/dt$ does not affect the equations of motion, but leads to a different definition for momentum i.e. $p = m \, dx/dt - x$ versus $p = m \, dx/dt$. (In general, $dG(x)/dt$ behaves in a similar manner.)

In quantum mechanics, $p \rightarrow -i \, d/dx$ and so $m \, dx/dt - x$ is the momentum used. Given a bound state wavefunction $W(x)$ written as a Fourier series, it is the new momentum which is represented by p . This p which is not $m \, dx/dt$ is involved in forming quantum resonances i.e. solutions of the Schrodinger equation. These resonances, however, do not necessarily affect the quantum partition function because the extra potential may create a phase, similar to the result of writing the Schrodinger equation viewed from a moving frame. Thus, one may have two different Hamiltonians physically equivalent to: $m/2 \, dx/dt \, dx/dt + V(x)$ namely: $p/2m + V(x)$ where $p = m \, dx/dt$ and $(p+x)(p+x)/2 + V(x)$ where $p = m \, dx/dt - x$. In this note, we examine the partition function from the Feynman path integral approach. Using this propagator approach one may find different partition functions for each case, even though $E = m/2 \, dx/dt \, dx/dt + V(x)$. Setting $X=Y$, however, yields a $P(x)$ which is the same. We consider the case of an extra potential of $d/dt \, G(x)$.

Different Lagrangians Yielding the Same Equations of Motion

It is possible for different Lagrangians to yield the same equations of motion e.g.:

$$1. \quad L = m/2 \, dx/dt \, dx/dt - V(x) \quad 2. \quad L = m/2 \, dx/dt \, dx/dt - ax \, dx/dt - V(x)$$

(Using $dG(x)/dt$ is a more general result.)

The momenta and Hamiltonians are, however, of different forms:

$$1. \quad p = m \, dx/dt \quad H = p^2/2m + V(x) \quad 2. \quad p = m \, dx/dt - ax \quad H = (p+ax)(p+ax)/2m + V(x)$$

It may be noted that both Hamiltonians are equivalent to $m/2 \, dx/dt \, dx/dt + V(x)$ because this is a conserved quantity. Only $V(x)$ accelerates the particle shifting kinetic energy into $V(x)$ type potential energy. If statistical mechanics is based only on kinetic energy and $V(x)$, one would expect the partition function to remain unchanged.

As a result, the time-independent Schrodinger equation for each system should be different and should yield different wavefunctions, but not necessarily different E_n 's if the extra potential is "equivalent" to viewing the Hamiltonian in a different frame.

According to the correspondence principle the classical density $cdx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity at x should match the quantum density envelope of $W^*n(x)Wn(x)$ for high n . $v(x)$, the classical

velocity is not affected by $ax dx/dt$ which does not change the equation of motion. Thus, for high n , solutions from both Hamiltonians should yield identical density envelopes. If a case 2 type solution, such as the Bohm-Aharonov yields only an extra phase as is the case of $dG(x)/dt$ (we later show), then this follows i.e.

$$(-i\hbar/dx + ax) \exp(-i \int_0^x dx' ax') W = \{-i\hbar(d/dx)W + ax - ax\} \exp(-i \int_0^x dx' ax')$$

Operating a second time yields: $(\hbar^2 p^2 W) \exp(-i \int_0^x dx' ax')$

In this case, E_n values are unchanged and the partition function with and without $ax dx/dt$ should remain the same.

Propagators

If one has two different Schrodinger equations, the Feynman propagators should differ for each i.e. $Q(t) \exp(i \text{Action})$. Changing i to -1 and T to ib where $b=1/T_p$, T_p being temperature converts the propagator into a partition function.

Consider cases 1 and 2 above with $V(x)=.5kx^2$, with the equations of motion being the same for each. $ax dx/dt$, leads to a different p and so apparently a different quantum resonance. In case 1, one has:

$$-1/2m \hbar^2 d^2/dx^2 W + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((1))$$

One may decompose W and V as Fourier series. $W(x)=\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $p=mdx/dt$. Thus, the physical resonance is between mdx/dt values at each x (because this is a statistical system) and $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ where k is the momentum of virtual photons. This is a certain kind of physical resonance and leads to a solution of ((1)).

For case 2:

$$1/2m \hbar^2 [-i\hbar/dx + ax][i\hbar/dx + ax] W_1(x) + V(x) W_1(x) = E W_1(x) \quad ((2))$$

In this case, $W_1(x) = \sum_p a_1(p) \exp(ipx)$ $ax = \sum_{k_1} b(k_1) \exp(i k_1 x)$ and $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

There are now virtual photons in both ax and $V(x)$ and these form a resonance with p which is $mdx/dt - ax$ and not mdx/dt . We argue that a different kind of physical resonance occurs in case ((2)), but this does not necessarily lead to a different solution of E_n 's. In particular, if only considers particle motion and the extra potential adds a phase, then a partition function representing the particle alone may remain unchanged even if the underlying physics differs.

It is possible to calculate propagators for the two cases i.e. $Q(t)\exp(i \text{Action})$ where $\text{Action} = \int dt L$ where L is the Lagrangian. If one changes i to -1 and T to ib where $b=1/T_p$ where

T_p is temperature, one obtains the partition function. Different propagators should lead to different partition functions.

For case 2, one may note that $\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} a x^2]$ which immediately yields a phase in the propagator, but a negative term in the partition function. The other part of the case 2 Lagrangian is identical to the case 1 situation because both case 1 and case 2 have the same equations of motion so $\frac{m}{2} \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} - \frac{1}{2} k x^2$ should yield the same result.

It should be noted that when calculating Lagrangians in the propagator approach, one uses:

$x(t) = X \frac{A(T-t)}{A(T)} + Y \frac{A(t-0)}{A(T)}$ where $A(t)$ is a solution of the classical equation of motion. $T_f = T$ $T_i = 0$. so $A(0) = 0$ ((2))

The oscillator propagator function is well known (3). For case 1, one has:

$$\text{Exp}\{i \left[\frac{1}{2} m \omega \frac{\cos(\omega T)}{\sin(\omega T)} (X^2 + Y^2) - XY \frac{m \omega}{\sin(\omega T)} \right]\} \quad ((3a))$$

For case 2:

$$\frac{1}{2} a x^2 \text{ (evaluated at 0 and T)} = \frac{1}{2} a \frac{1}{[A(T)A(0)]} \{ X^2 A(T-t)A(T-t) + Y^2 A(t)A(t) + 2XY A(t)A(T-t) \}$$

$$= (-X^2 + Y^2) \text{ because } A(0) = 0$$

$$\text{Exp}\{i \left[\frac{1}{2} m \omega \frac{\cos(\omega T)}{\sin(\omega T)} (X^2 + Y^2) - XY \frac{m \omega}{\sin(\omega T)} + \frac{1}{2} a (X^2 - Y^2) \right]\} \quad ((3b))$$

To create partition functions for the two cases, i becomes -1 and T becomes β where $\beta = 1/T_p$, T_p being temperature. To calculate expectations values of functions of x , X and Y in ((3a)) and ((3b)) are set to x ((2)). In such a case, the unnormalized $P(x)$ is the same for cases 1 and 2.

Expectation of x^2

Setting $X=Y=x$ to obtain an unnormalized $P(x)$, one sees that $\frac{1}{2} a (X^2 - Y^2)$ becomes 0. Thus:

$$\text{Case 1: } \langle x^2 \rangle = \text{variance} = 1/(2B) \quad \text{Case 2: } \langle x^2 \rangle = 1/[2(B)]$$

Thus, the quantum mechanical expectation of x^2 is the same for the two cases as are the equations of motion.

General Extra Potential in the Form $\frac{d}{dt} G(x)$.

The extra potential $\frac{dx}{dt}$ is an example of a more general form namely $\frac{d}{dt} G(x)$. It contributes nothing to the classical equations of motion i.e.

$$-d/dt [d/d (dx/dt) d/dt G(x)] + d/dx d/dt G(x) = -d/dt dG/dx + d/dx [dG/dx dx/dt] = 0$$

The contribution to $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ is:

$[G(x)]$ evaluated at $t=T$ and $t=0$ where $x(t)$ is given by ((2))

If $G(x)$ is written as a power series in x , then:

$$x(t)^n = \{ (XA(T-t))^n + (YA(t))^n + \text{mixed terms with X and Y} \} / [A(T)^n]$$

Given that $A(0)=0$, any mixed term vanishes at both $t=0$ and $t=T$, and one has:

$$-(X)^n + (Y)^n \quad \text{because } A(T-t) \text{ yields } A(T) \text{ for } t=0 \text{ (hence the minus) and } A(t) \text{ for } t=T.$$

When creating $P(x)$, one sets $X=Y$ as in (3) and so all powers cancel and there is no contribution from a $d/dt G(x)$ type of extra potential to the partition function or $P(x, T_p)$.

Thus, even though the physical resonances seem to be very different, the partition function remains unchanged in such a situation as the Hamiltonian describes only the motion of the particle in both cases i.e. $m/2 dx/dt dx/dt + V(x)$.

It may also be seen that an extra potential of the form $d/dt G(x) = dG/dx dx/dt$ leads to a phase in the wavefunction. $p = m dx/dt - dG/dx$ so $m dx/dt = p + dG/dx$. The Hamiltonian $H = p dx/dt - L = m/2 dx/dt dx/dt + V(x) = 1/2m (p - dG/dx)(p - dG/dx) + V(x)$. $[p - dG/dx] \exp(-i \text{Integral } dx_1 (0,x) dG/dx_1) = [pW] \exp(-i \text{Integral } dx_1 (0,x))$. Operating again with $(p + dG/dx)$ yields $[ppW] \exp(-i \text{Integral } dx_1 (0,x))$. Thus, a $d/dt G(x)$ extra potential leads to an $\exp(i \text{ phase})$ factor added to the wavefunction. The partition function and density remain unchanged.

Classical Expectation of xx and pp

One may examine cases 1 and 2 in a classical scenario. Consider the potential $ax dx/dt + .5kxx$. For case 1, the usual Boltzmann distribution $C \exp(- (pp/2m + .5kxx)/T_p)$ leads to two Gaussian integrals, one in x and one in p .

For case 2, the distribution is: $C \exp[- ((p-ax)(p-ax)/2m + .5kxx)/T_p]$.

p no longer has the meaning of $m dx/dt$, but dp/dx also reflects this new p . For a fixed x , $\exp(- (p+ax)(p+ax)/2m)$ is a shifted Gaussian. Its area does not depend on the origin, only on the standard deviation. Thus, it is the same for all x , so:

$$\text{Case 2: } \langle xx \rangle = \text{Integral } dx \ xx \ \exp(-.5kxx/T_p) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is the same for cases 1 and 2, so in the classical case, one does not see a difference for the shifted Gaussian for a function of x . For a function of p , however, one must change variables $p \rightarrow p - ax + ax$ so for pp one has $(p - ax)(p - ax) + aaxx + 2(p - ax)ax$. The last term integrates to 0, but $aaxx$ is an extra term which must be integrated. Thus:

Case 2: $\langle pp \rangle = \langle pp \text{ Case 1} \rangle + \int dx \, xx \exp(-.5kxx/Tp) C1$ where $C1$ is a normalization constant. It may be noted, however, that p has a different meaning in the two cases. For case 1, $p = mdx/dt$ while for case 2 $p = mdx/dt - ax$. Thus:

Case 2 $\langle (mdx/dt - ax)(mdx/dt - ax) \rangle = \langle mdx/dt \, mdx/dt \rangle + \int dx \, xx \exp(-.5kxx/Tp) C1$

This is the same result for: Case 1: $\langle (mdx/dt - ax)(mdx/dt - ax) \rangle$.

In the classical case it seems that there is no difference for the $axdx/dt$ extra potential.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that an extra potential term of the form $axdx/dt$ (or $dG(x)/dt$) that does not change classical equations of motion, may still change the quantum resonance. In other words the Hamiltonians for a Lagrangian with $axdx/dt$ and one without differ. This, however, does not necessarily mean different E_n 's because the extra potential may be related to a Schrodinger equation for a system viewed in a different frame. Physically, we argue that different resonances occur. In the case of no $axdx/dt$, $W(x) = \sum a(p) \exp(ipx)$. P represents mdx/dt of a p particle and there are statistical interactions with the virtual photons of $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. In the case of an $axdx/dt$ present, $p = mdx/dt - ax$ so there is a kind of combined momentum which interacts with the virtual photons of $ax = \sum_k k1 a1(k1) \exp(ik1x)$ as well as with those of $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

We calculate the partition function, using the propagator approach for $V(x) = .5kxx$ with both an $axdx/dt$ present and absent and find the same $P(x)$ and $\langle xx \rangle$ values. The partition function, follows from the Feynman propagator $\exp(iAction)$ with i changed to -1 and T to $b = 1/Tp$ where Tp is temperature.

We also consider the same situation for the classical case, but find that $axdx/dt$ neither changes the equations of motion nor $\langle xx \rangle$ or $\langle pp \rangle$ where $p = mdx/dt - ax$.

References

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